

**EXPERIMENTAL STUDY OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF DEEP
ENAMEL FLUORIDATION DURING THE SECONDARY
MINERALIZATION OF ENAMEL OF PERMANENT TEETH.**

Daminova Sh.B.

Tashpulatova X.A.

Tashkent State Dental Institute

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The prevalence of caries among children and adults is 98-100% according to epidemiological studies [1]. This pathology is a defect in the integrity of the dental hard tissue and has a significant negative impact on the aesthetic and functional condition of the tooth-jaw system.

The initial stages of caries are associated with demineralization caused by acid on the tooth surface and exotoxins of microorganisms in dental caries. This has been proven in many studies [2].

Stain stage caries is the first stage of the caries process, which has the opportunity to stop the rapid demineralization process in the hard tissue of the tooth and restore the optimal mineral content. It is known that ion exchange and diffusion processes always occur in enamel at the structural level. Hydroxyapatite crystals are highly sensitive to the electrochemical composition of intercellular fluid, blood, oral fluid, and show 5 features of their participation in ion exchange. The preservation of the protein matrix in the enamel crystal grids and the possibility of filling the mineral deficiency serve as a pathogenetic basis for carrying out remineralization therapy [6,7,9,10]. For this purpose, calcium and fluoride-preserving drugs are widely used. Many scientific studies have proven the effectiveness and safety of fluorides. The caries-prophylactic effect of fluorides is multifaceted: the formation of a calcium fluoride layer on the surface and subsurface layer of enamel reduces demineralization and, together with stimulation of hard tissue remineralization, reduces the release of acidic products of bacteria in the biofilm [3,4,5,8].

The fact that there is insufficient information in the literature about the choice of methods of treatment and prevention of enamel white spot caries according to the hygienic condition of the oral cavity, led to the following scientific investigation.

Purpose: to evaluate the effectiveness of fluoride-preserving remineralizing drugs in the treatment and prevention of enamel caries of permanent teeth.

Material and examination methods: 2 preparations were taken as remineralizing preparations for the examination: 1) "Denta-Fluo" Dentals Pharma, Uzbekistan; 2) Fluorine varnish Omega dent, Russia.

The examination was conducted in 32 patients. The patients were somatically healthy children aged 11-15 years. They are children in the stage of orthodontic treatment, children whose permanent premolar teeth should be removed according to the instructions were selected. All patients and their parents were contracted for the examination. An experimental model was created to evaluate the effectiveness of the used drugs. For this purpose, 15 healthy permanent teeth obtained according to the instructions were used.

For 3 months, artificial enamel demineralization was formed in 5 samples of teeth until teeth were extracted. The specimens were stored in 3 separate sealed boxes (5 in each box) with artificial saliva (T. Fusayama, 1975). The teeth were cleaned from caries using fluoride-free paste and brushes, air-dried, isolated from saliva. A 3 mm diameter area was separated on the equatorial surface of the teeth, and the rest of the vestibular surface was covered with liquid cofferdam. The demineralization center was treated with 37% orthophosphoric acid for 2 minutes. Orthophosphoric acid causes the loss of mineral components in the enamel prisms and in the inter-prism space. Patients were divided into 3 groups:

- 1) 5 samples of healthy teeth (control group)
- 2) a group of 5 artificial demineralized teeth fluoridated by the surface fluoridation method (ordinary Fluorine varnish);
- 3) Group of artificial demineralized teeth (Denta Fluo) fluoridated by 5 deep fluoridation methods.

Enamel samples of the first group were examined at the beginning of the experiment. The samples of the second group were treated with "Denta-Fluo" preparation for deep fluoridation of enamel. Samples were processed at the beginning of the experiment and after 6 months of experiment. Enamel samples of the third group were taken for control and were not treated. At the end of the experiment, enamel samples of the second and third groups were examined.

Enamel samples were studied at the beginning of the experiment and after 6 months. In the first stage of the research, the surface of the samples was analyzed using a scanning electron microscope (SEM, ZEISS Evo 10, Germany), and in the second stage, the chemical composition was determined using the additional detection capability of this device (EDS spectrometer and WDS spectrometer). Results were calculated in weight percent.

Research results: Research results show that after 6 months of deep fluoridation, calcium (20.47 ± 1.07 to 28.5 ± 1.05), oxygen (54.09 ± 6.08 to 35 to $.5 \pm 3.75$), significant changes occur in the composition of carbon (from 8.22 ± 5.73). ± 0.52), fluorine (from 0.1 ± 0.03 to 12.5 ± 1.97), magnesium (from 0.21 ± 0.04 to 0.7 ± 0.09), sodium ($0, 58 \pm 0.07$ to 0.3 ± 0.05), silicon (0.1 ± 0.03 to 0.3 ± 0.05), silicon (0.1 ± 0.03 to $12.5 \pm$ up to 1.97),), the calcium/phosphorus ratio (from 1.38 ± 0.08 to 2.11 ± 0.12) is located in the superficial layer of immature permanent tooth enamel ($r < 0.05$).

Increased mineralization of permanent tooth enamel after deep fluoridation was confirmed by scanning electron microscopy. After deep fluoridation of the enamel, the relief of the enamel is smoothed, the surface appears smooth. It can be seen that the craters of the enamel prisms have been significantly reduced compared to the initial level, with or without closed surfaces.

Summary. Thus, the results of the study show that the enamel of recently erupted teeth is not completely mineralized, and therefore their resistance to caries is significantly lower. The chemical composition of the surface layer of tooth enamel changed in a positive way after the application of deep enamel fluoridation methods. Reaching the optimal level of enamel mineralization under the influence of deep fluoridation occurs within 6 months after the experiment. Thus, exogenous agents for the prevention of dental caries (deep enamel fluoridation) can be recommended for clinical use immediately after the eruption of teeth within 12 months (1-2 times a year).

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